

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Externalisation of EU Migration Policies: The Case of Cooperation in the Georgian Citizens' Returns from Poland

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List of Abbreviations

AVR	Assisted voluntary return
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease
EaP	Eastern Partnership
EC	European Commission
ENIGMMA	Enhancing Georgia's Migration Management
ENIGMMA-2	Sustaining Migration Management in Georgia
ENP	European Neighbourhood Policy
EU	European Union
Frontex	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
IDIs	Individual In-depth Interviews
IDPs	Internally displaced persons
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
n.d.	No date
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
OFII	French Office for Immigration and Integration
RCMES	Readmission Case Management Electronic System
SCMI	State Commission on Migration Issues
UK	United Kingdom

Abstract

Migration remains an essential factor in the dynamics of EU politics. This working paper aims to broaden our understanding of the cooperation mechanism between the EU and Georgia in the context of the EU's externalisation of migration policies. We focus on the EU Member State – Poland, the sending country, and Georgia, the country receiving returnees, one of six Eastern Partnership members. We pay particular attention to the returns of Georgian citizens from Poland (with various levels of coercion), as they represent one of the largest groups of returned foreigners under Poland's return practices. At the same time, Georgia remains a country strongly committed to integration with the EU structures. The paper draws on the qualitative material and data collected during fieldwork on Georgia from February to May 2024. The main part of the research was carried out on-site in Tbilisi. Follow-up interviews were conducted in Poland, mainly online. We conducted 25 individual in-depth interviews with representatives of international organisations, public institutions, non-governmental organisations, and other experts who had knowledge about returns to Georgia and the reintegration of Georgian citizens. This work was supplemented with desk research regarding the legal framework and return infrastructure in Poland and Georgia and the reintegration framework in the latter. The results reveal the untapped potential of the cooperation between Polish and Georgian institutions, which could make the returns more satisfying for migrants and – consequently – more efficient for the EU policies. The paper suggests, among other things, strengthening 1) information dissemination to prospective returnees before departure and 2) the role of local organisations in Georgia in assessing business plans within the reintegration programmes.

Keywords: return migration, EU migration policies, Georgia, Poland, externalisation of migration policies

1. Introduction¹

Since the so-called migration crisis with the outbreak in 2015, migration remains one of the most important factors shaping the dynamics of European Union (EU) politics. The European Commission (EC), as early as 2011, declared that ‘migration is now firmly at the top of the EU’s political agenda’ (EC 2011). The EU policies in the field of migration and home affairs are based on the security principle, assuming the need for effective border control (Huysmans 2006; Delcour 2013; Trojanowska-Strzęboszewska 2018). Ensuring such a control pertains not only to regulating the entry of migrants into the EU territory but also their returns to the countries of origin. Importantly, this paper avoids using a dichotomy between forced and voluntary returns, assuming that various levels of coercion are present in the case of each return (Şahin-Mencütek et al. 2023).

To ensure the highest possible level of effectiveness of its migration policy, the EU externalises the application of migration control in the form of readmission agreements, visa facilitation agreements, and mobility partnerships being signed with different countries (van Munster, Sterkx 2006; Delcour 2013; Papagianni 2013; Tittel-Mosser 2019). Externalisation is, thus, understood in this working paper as seeking cooperation with non-EU countries on migration issues (Reslow 2018).

Regarding irregularly staying third-country nationals, the EU’s migration policy focuses on efforts to effectively return this group of migrants and this approach, which remains a priority for the Member States practices regarding migratory issues (EMN 2017). However, the number of migrants returned remains much lower than the figures of those ordered to leave. In the years 2021-2022, in the EU, the former did not exceed a quarter of the latter (Eurostat 2023). Interestingly, the figures of migrants ordered to leave and those returned vary in terms of nationalities (and returning countries). While the citizens of Georgia are not within the top three of those ordered to leave in the last quarter of 2022 (see Figure 1.), they occupy the second place among the returnees (see Figure 2.). Moreover, while among the top three nationalities of those ordered to leave are only non-European countries, among the top three of those returned are two EU candidates: besides Georgia, there is also Albania (Eurostat 2023; see Figure 2.). This leads to the questions of how the potential accession to the EU impacts the cooperation in the return of migrants and what it means for the externalisation of the EU migration policies.

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FIGURE 1: TOP 3 NATIONALITIES ORDERED TO LEAVE THE EU IN Q4 2022

Source: Eurostat (2023).

FIGURE 2: TOP 3 NATIONALITIES RETURNED FROM THE EU IN Q4 2022

Source: Eurostat (2023).

The returns of Georgian citizens are an especially salient element of migratory policies in some Member States. In Poland, since 2022, this group of migrants has become important for the country's return practices. At the same time, Georgia (despite recent political unrest²) remains a country strongly committed to integration with the EU structures. Since 14 December 2023, the candidate status of Georgia has been officially confirmed by the EC, following an application by Georgia in March 2022 (European Commission n.d.). Hence, Georgia has been chosen for the case study due to its ongoing integration process with the EU and the relevance of this country for the EU return policy.

This working paper aims to broaden our understanding of the cooperation mechanism between the EU and Georgia in the context of the EU's externalisation of migration policies. We focus on the EU Member State – Poland, the sending country, and Georgia, the country receiving returnees, one of six Eastern Partnership (EaP) members. We pay particular

² The proposed bill on tightening control over the NGOs led to mass demonstrations in May 2024. For more on the illiberal reforms in Georgia see Brender (2024).

attention to the returns of Georgian citizens from Poland (with various levels of coercion), as they represent one of the largest groups of returned foreigners under Poland's return practices. At the same time, Georgia remains a country strongly committed to integration with the EU structures. The paper draws on the qualitative material and data collected during fieldwork regarding Georgia from February to May 2024. The main part of the research was carried out on-site in Tbilisi. Follow-up interviews were conducted in Poland, mainly online. We conducted 25 individual in-depth interviews (IDIs) with representatives of international organisations, public institutions, non-governmental organisations and other experts having knowledge about returns to Georgia and the reintegration of Georgian citizens upon return. The interviews were conducted using the interview guidelines and were preceded by obtaining clearance from the Ethics Committee of the Centre of Migration Research at the University of Warsaw. The principles of informed consent and anonymous participation were crucial for the research team when conducting the interviews. This work was supplemented with desk research regarding the legal framework and return infrastructure in Poland and Georgia and the reintegration framework in the latter.

The results reveal the untapped potential of cooperation between EU Member States and Georgian institutions, which could make returns providing more opportunities for migrants, especially in terms of reintegration and—as a consequence—more effective from the point of view of EU policies. The analysis suggests, *among other things*, strengthening both the information dissemination before departure and the role of local organisations in Georgia in assessing business plans within the reintegration programmes.

The paper proceeds as follows. The context of the externalisation of EU migration policies is discussed at the beginning. Next, the practical dimension of migration in Georgia and the EU-Georgia cooperation is presented regarding both returns per se and reintegration, which constitutes a crucial factor in an effective return policy. Based on this analysis, the working paper points out the gaps in the current application of the return policy in the scope under study and offers recommendations to address them. In the conclusion, the broader dimension of the externalisation of the EU migration policies is briefly analysed, drawing on the research results.

2. Background

2.1. Externalisation of the EU Migration Policies

As already mentioned, the EU's externalisation of the migration policy is understood in this working paper as seeking cooperation by the EU institutions or the Member States with non-EU countries on migration issues (Reslow 2018). In the case of the EU, the main forms of externalisation are readmission agreements, visa facilitation agreements, and mobility partnerships (van Munster, Sterkx 2006; Delcour 2013; Papagianni 2013; Tittel-Mosser 2019) including very practical dimensions in the form of covering costs of bureaucratic procedures and detention facilities (Himmrich 2018: 4). Important examples of externalisation were the EU-Turkey deal of March 2016 (Pastore, Roman 2020), the cooperation arrangements launched in the summer of 2017 between Italian and Libyan authorities (Cassarino 2018), and a recent Italian agreement with Albania (Human Rights Watch 2024).

There is no strictly defined role for non-EU countries cooperating in the internalisation process. Ali Bilgic (2011) claims that the EU envisaged such roles for the external partners as filters of migration flow and asylum claims as well as a 'dumping ground' for unauthorised

migrants. The exact role assigned to a given country depends on its geographical location and negotiating capacities, which are, in turn, a result of different political settings.

Mobility Partnerships based on the EU's Global Approach to Migration and Mobility are a complex solution applied within the externalisation. These partnerships are focused on combining the prevention of unauthorised migration with looking for ways of legal migration and boosting the nexus between migration and development. As such, this measure should lead to a 'Win-Win-Win' situation for all the parties involved: migrants as well as sending and receiving countries (Broczka, Paulhart 2015). Therefore, the external dimension of the EU migration policy is not based solely on deterrence and combating unauthorised flows; it also envisages creating legal alternatives; however, returns of unauthorised migrants have priority over other goals (Pastore, Roman 2020). As the EC stated in 2016, efficient returns would be essential in the case of partnership with non-EU countries (European Council 2016a; 2016b). It aligns with the general principle of the EU migratory policies based on security and effective border control (Huysmans 2006; Delcour 2013; Trojanowska-Strzęboszewska 2018).

Migration issues remain salient also under the European Neighbourhood Policy (ENP) (Delcour 2013). Within the EaP (defined as an institutionalised forum for EU cooperation with Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus³, Georgia, Moldova, and Ukraine), the Panel on Migration and Asylum has functioned since 2011 with the objective to 'strengthen the asylum and migration systems of Eastern partners and advance the dialogue on migration and asylum issues between the Eastern partners and the EU, as well as amongst the Eastern partners' (European Commission n.d. b). This kind of political mechanism can be understood as an example of trans-regional governance, which, as argued by Laure Decour (2013), links different regions, contributing to replacing formal multilateral bonds with a global institutional framework of migration governance. It is claimed that the EU is attempting to use the ENP to keep the identified threats out of the EU's door, which is being achieved, e.g. by exporting policy norms and templates to the cooperating countries (Balzacq 2009). Eastern European countries (including the Caucasus region) are an important part of the ENP, with six countries cooperating with the EU in the EaP scheme since 2009. Although the priority for the EU, in terms of preventing unauthorised migration, is Sub-Saharan Africa, not the post-Soviet area (Pastore, Roman 2020), the readmission agreements were initially signed mostly with Eastern European neighbours, which proves their importance for this kind of cooperation (Delcour 2013).⁴

Seeking solutions based on the externalisation measures was reinforced by the failure of internal EU solutions to migration challenges, such as the relocation scheme after 2015 (Pastore, Roman 2020). Externalisation can also be seen as a chance for the EU Member States to overcome obstacles to implementing more restrictive policies on migration (Lavenex 2006). On the other hand, for non-EU countries, it is an opportunity 'to capitalise on securitised perceptions of migration by positioning themselves as proxy implementers of restrictive migration policies of the EU' (Pastore, Roman 2020: 135). However, this pertains mostly to the transit role of some countries (e.g. Libya or Morocco in relation to migrants from Sub-Saharan

³ After 2020 presidential elections, the EU-Belarus relations were reviewed and revised by the EU. The EU's support post-2020 has been reoriented towards non-state actors. Minsk regime's involvement in the full-scale Russian aggression against Ukraine led to the imposition of a series of individual sanctions and sectoral measures on Belarus. In 2021, the country's participation in the EaP was suspended by the Belarusian authorities. All this resulted in the factual suspension of readmission cooperation with Belarus. For more details, see EU website, e.g. European Commission (n.d. c).

⁴ It should be also noted that the obligation to readmit not only own nationals, but also third country nationals and stateless persons who transited through the given state was problematic for South Mediterranean countries in the case of readmission agreements (Delcour 2013).

Africa), not the role of the countries of origin, as in the case of Georgia. Regarding the countries of origin, the interest in enhancing cooperation on returns lies mainly in the incentives made by the EU to develop possibilities of legal migration. In these terms, externalisation should be seen as a ‘bargaining process’ between the EU Member States and third parties (Pastore, Roman 2020: 139). However, as Laure Delcour (2013) points out, the governments of the state willing to join the Union possess less capacity to negotiate the conditions of cooperation than the others. As recent developments on the Polish (Lithuanian and Latvian)-Belarusian border show, this ‘bargaining process’ may mean threatening destabilisation by instrumental use of migrants smuggled through the borders (Górczyńska 2021).

The externalisation of migration policies impacts both the situation of migrants and the cooperating non-EU countries; its consequences are more far-reaching than expected and include side effects (Delcour 2013) or are considered to be a ‘road to nowhere’ since they have failed to prevent a new surge in irregular migration or even contributed to this new crisis (Martini, Megerisi 2023). Ferruccio Pastore and Emanuela Roman (2020) argue that externalisation shaped the number of migrants crossing the Mediterranean routes and political dynamics in African states. It did not stop the migration but changed the routes, and it also had a detrimental effect on the livelihoods of migrant families by curbing remittances (Delcour 2013). Externalisation was likewise criticised from the human rights perspective regarding deterring migrants from the EU borders (Gammeltoft-Hansen, Hathaway 2015; Spijkerboer 2013). In this regard, externalisation was accused of leaving migrants in the hands of authoritarian governments and at risk of chain refoulement (Delcour 2013). The object of criticism was also subcontracting other than state actors for implementing migration policies, seen as a ‘business’ or ‘industry’ (Andersson 2014) serving to ‘maximise the effectiveness and minimise the costs and visibility of measures and operations’ (Pastore, Roman 2020: 138).

2.3. A Brief Overview of the Emigration from and Returns to Georgia

Georgia is known as an emigration country. After regaining independence in 1991, high unemployment, poverty, and low salaries led many Georgian citizens to seek better opportunities abroad (Khishtovani et al. 2022). Despite the economic development in recent years, the outflow of people from Georgia increased by 7% from 2010 to 2020, exceeding 860,000 emigrants, which is 23% of the country’s population (Khishtovani et al. 2022). The main destination for Georgian migrants, as of 2017, was Russia (approx. 450,000), followed by Greece (approx. 81,000) and Ukraine (approx. 65,000) (SCMI 2019). Around three-fourths of Georgian emigrants reside in post-Soviet countries, and this figure remains relatively stable. From 2010 to 2020, the share of the post-Soviet area as a destination for Georgian emigration slightly declined from 75% to 72%, while the shares of EU countries and the UK increased from 20% to 21% (Khishtovani et al. 2022). The main EU destinations for Georgians in 2017 were – besides already mentioned Greece – Germany (approx. 23,000), Cyprus (approx. 16,000), and Italy (approx. 12,000) (SCMI 2019).

The 2017 EU-Georgia visa liberalisation agreement was followed by an increase in concerns about the activities of Georgian organised crime groups in the EU (IOM 2019). The number of asylum applications from Georgians in the EU/Schengen countries increased since the introduction of visa-free travel to this area for Georgian citizens. However, around 95% of these applications have been considered unfounded and rejected (as of 2018), and some EU Member States placed Georgia on the list of safe countries (SCMI 2019). Data from the Polish

migration agency (Office for Foreigners) show that in 2019-2023, there were 375 Georgian citizens applying for international protection, but none was recognised as a refugee, and only one person received subsidiary protection (Office for Foreigners n.d.)

Considering Georgia’s emigration character, it is not surprising that the Georgian diaspora remains an important asset of the country, especially in economic terms but also in the case of advocacy for the country (SCMI 2020). Remittances from migrants working abroad play a salient role in Georgia’s economy. For instance, in 2018, as many as 57% of Georgians abroad were sending money to their family in Georgia, and the total monetary value of remittances was higher than that of foreign direct investment in this country (SCMI 2019). The diaspora’s saliency for economic growth is evident as remittances more than doubled from 2015 to 2021 (Khishtovani et al. 2022). In 2008, the Office of the State Minister for Diaspora Affairs was created, and in 2016, it was incorporated into the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Georgia. The Georgian policy on diaspora seems to be balanced and encouraging to return.

At the same time, there was also an increase in the number of Georgians being refused entry to the EU/Schengen states, notably for reasons such as failing to justify their purpose and conditions of stay. Between 2015 and 2016, Poland was the first and, in the years 2017-2018, the second (after Greece) EU country to have the highest number of refusals of entry issued to Georgian citizens (SCMI 2019). Also, in 2018, Poland occupied fourth place among the EU Member States, with the highest number of Georgian citizens found illegally staying in the country (SCMI 2019). Since recently, Georgian citizens have dominated Poland’s forced return policy (see Figure 3.), and this country was the fourth in the EU regarding the number of issued readmission requests to Georgia (see Figure 3.).

Figure 3: Foreigners leaving Poland based on administrative decisions in 2022

Source: Border Guard statistics. <https://www.strazgraniczna.pl/pl/granica/statystyki-sg/2206,Statystyki-SG.html> (last accessed 26 April 2024).

Figure 4: Readmission Requests received by Georgia from EU Member States in 2023

Country	Received	Approved	Rejected
Germany	2771	2760	11
France	635	633	2
Greece	175	173	2
Poland	106	106	0
Italy	97	97	0
The other countries	399	394	5
Total	4183	4163	20

Source: Information received upon request from the Ministry of Interior of Georgia (2024).

Return migration constitutes an important element of the Georgian migratory landscape. The number of Georgians ordered to leave the EU increased from 6,345 in 2015 to 9,754 in 2018, and in the same period, the growth of figures regarding forced and voluntary returns was even higher – in sum, from 3,140 up to 6,625 (SCMI 2019). The large number of returns was especially visible as a corollary of the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, in 2020, Georgia observed a positive net migration balance, which was quite an exceptional situation (Khishtovani et al. 2022). According to accessible data, as many as 23,000 Georgian citizens formerly residing abroad moved back into the country only in the first six months of 2021 (IOM 2021a). Yet, this phenomenon did not change the country of emigration character of Georgia.

2.3. Reintegration Infrastructure in Georgia

The increase in returns also contributed to the increase in the number of beneficiaries of reintegration programmes. However, not all returnees are entitled to reintegration programmes and not all of those entitled participate in them. The most important eligibility criteria for being a beneficiary of the reintegration programmes are linked to time spent abroad.

For instance, in 2015, there were 560 beneficiaries of reintegration programmes in Georgia, while in 2018, this number increased to 815. These numbers are not high compared to the figures on returns (3,140 and 6,625, respectively). Almost half (45%) of all beneficiaries of reintegration in this period came from Greece, and other significant countries in this regard were Germany (24%) and Belgium (15%). Poland occupied the seventh position (SCMI 2019). Most reintegration beneficiaries are returnees from EU states (SCMI 2020).

The reintegration of returnees was made the key priority for the Georgian government, along with preventing irregular migration to Georgia and applying for asylum by Georgian citizens in the EU. As Georgia’s Migration Strategy declares, ‘it is the country’s priority to encourage the return of Georgian citizens from abroad and facilitate their reintegration upon return’ (SCMI 2020: 36). However, at the same time, the Strategy envisages an important role for the Georgian diaspora, stating that the Georgian constitutes ‘a valuable contribution to

Georgia's socio-economic development' (SCMI 2020: 39). As a public administration worker told us, 'it will be not clever to call all Georgians to return to their homeland because, uh, it's we have a not good enough resources to offer for everyone somehow houses, accommodation, job, etc.' (IDI_GE_11). This proves that reintegration is not only a matter of the individual situation of a given migrant but it heavily depends on the structural factors in the country of origin. For instance, even the best business project would not be successful if there is no supply on the local market for the offered products or services. Because of that, the return policy is strongly overlapping with economic and development policies.

Head of the Policy Department in the Ministry of Health, Labour and Social Affairs of Georgia, Giorgi Chavchavadze, stressed the importance of reintegration and pointed out development, social protection, education, and health programmes as crucial to establishing effective reintegration policy (IOM 2021a). The most common form of reintegration assistance is a grant to set an income generating project (usually a small business), while an identified shortage exists in psychological help (IOM 2021b). According to the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), the outcomes of Georgian returnees are poorer than global averages (IOM 2021b).

3. Externalisation of the EU Migration Policies – The Case of Returns to Georgia

3.1. Cooperation Between the EU and Georgia in Combating Irregular Migration and Performing Returns

The integration of Georgia with the EU is an essential factor in developing migration policies in this country. As Georgia's Migration Strategy declares, 'development of migration management system in Georgia was given a strong impetus by an accelerated process of Georgia's approximation with the European Union' (SCMI 2020: 6). The cooperation between Georgia and the EU is shaped by different arrangements: on the EU-Georgia level as well as within both bilateral and multilateral agreements between the Georgian government and various EU Member States. Since November 2009, Georgia has cooperated with sixteen EU Member States within a *Joint Declaration on cooperation in the framework of EU's Partnership for Mobility*. This initiative focuses on fighting against illegal migration and the promotion of legal migration paths. Readmission and reintegration are important elements of this cooperation. Moreover, it provides arrangements for circular migration, inevitably linked to returns and re-returns (SCMI n.d. a).

In the case of Georgia, an effective policy on returns is a condition for such incentives as visa regime liberalisation. The EU-Georgia visa liberalisation agreement recognises that 'visa facilitation should not lead to illegal migration' and pays 'special attention to security and readmission' (Agreement 2011a: preamble). This agreement was signed together with the one on readmission (Agreement 2011b). It was decided that it shall only enter into force on the date of the entry into force of the agreement on readmission (Agreements 2011a: art. 14). Although there is an emphasis on reciprocity in the agreement (Agreement 2011b: preamble), the obvious aim of the deals were the effective returns of Georgian citizens from the EU rather than *vice versa*. The readmission agreement stipulates means of evidence regarding nationality of a migrant (art. 8), time limits of the readmission procedure (art. 10), transfer modalities and

modes of transportation (art. 11), as well as transit procedures (art. 14). It also sets up Joint Readmission Committee with the competences of monitoring the application of the agreement, deciding on implementing arrangements ‘necessary for the uniform application’ thereof, proposing amendments and exchanging information (art. 18). The full implementation of the readmission agreement was also included in the EU-Georgia Association Agreement (2014: art. 16). Therefore, the effective returns remain an expectation from Georgia in case of the general integration process with the EU.

Two crucial EU-funded projects related to migration were implemented in Georgia across the Mobility Partnership and visa facilitation scheme: ENIGMMA and ENIGMMA-2. The first one stands for *Enhancing Georgia’s Migration Management* and was implemented in 2013-2017 by the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD). The project focused on developing a labour migration strategy, circular migration, and diaspora involvement. It also envisaged expanding the analytical capacities of Georgian migration institutions (SCMI n.d. b). The same agency implemented the second project, *Sustaining Migration Management in Georgia*, in 2016-2023. Despite the lack of explicit focus on returns, the project aimed at minimising the risks of irregular migration, developing ‘legal channels for regularisation of Georgian migrants in irregular situation’, and generally strengthening cooperation of migration agencies (Eu4Georgia.eu n.d.). According to our interviewed stakeholders, both projects considerably improved data protection in the area of migration in Georgia, so they not only led to more effective returns from the sending country’s point of view but also had some positive impact on the rights of migrants.

The EU praised Georgia for the implementation of readmission procedures. During a conference organised by the IOM on the occasion of the third anniversary of the EU-Georgia visa liberalisation agreement, EU Ambassador Carl Hartzell claimed that ‘visa-free travel available to citizens of Georgia has demonstrated its worth by bringing the EU and Georgia closer together’. The general feeling, he noted, is that Georgia has demonstrated a laudable commitment to cooperating with the authorities of EU Member States in decreasing the pressure of irregular migration (IOM 2019).

Apart from cooperation at the EU level, bilateral agreements are also an essential part of the externalisation of migration policies by EU Member States. Germany plays an important role in this regard, having an agreement with Georgia regarding seasonal workers (Agenda.ge 2021) and an agreement to facilitate the returns of rejected asylum applicants (AA 2023). Importantly, the agreement facilitating returns offers academic exchange programmes for Georgians (AA 2023). This aligns with the policy of offering incentives in exchange for readmission enhancements.

Some projects in the field of returns are co-funded by the EU and a sending member state. This was the case of the project Strengthening the Development Potential of the EU Mobility Partnership in Georgia through Targeted Circular Migration and Diaspora Mobilization funded by the EU and the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development and implemented in 2013-2016 (SCMI n.d. c). The co-funded (by the EU and Member States) cooperation also included returns of Georgian citizens. According to our respondents, assisted voluntary returns (AVR) are funded by the EU funds and the governments of the sending countries. Within this form of cooperation, combined flights are also organised. As one expert involved in the assistance for returnees in Georgia said, ‘in most cases, all the migrants from the European Union [were] combined in Germany and they were deported from this state [to Georgia]’ (IDI_GE_14-15). Furthermore, as one of the public administration employees told us: ‘Minister of Internal Affairs is in charge of this. They’re

sending a plane with staff, for example, in Poland, in Germany, and they accompany these returnees on the [basis of the] readmission agreement' (IDI_GE_11). As noted by our interviewees, representatives of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Georgia participate in the Collecting Return Operations organised by Frontex and ensure escort for Georgian returnees (IDI_GE_21). Representatives of the Georgian Ombudsman randomly monitor the flights.

Also, with the EU funding and support of IOM, the Readmission Case Management Electronic System (RCMES) has been developed. This system is a web-based, secure platform which facilitates the exchange of necessary information with partner countries and competent Georgian authorities and significantly simplifies the procedure of receiving and processing requests on readmission (IDI_GE_21). Thus, the externalisation of the EU policy on return also involved the development of technologies and capacities of Georgian migration agencies.

3.2. Cooperation Between the EU and Georgia in Organising the Reintegration of Returnees

Overview

Reintegration assistance after return to Georgia is an important element of Georgian migration policy. The *State Programme for Supporting Reintegration of Returned Georgian Migrants*⁵ offers assistance such as medical services, social projects, vocational education, and temporary livelihood to Georgians irregularly residing abroad for more than one year and rejected or accepted asylum applicants. As observed by a public administration employee interviewed, the state reintegration programme was elaborated in cooperation with the IOM. The project also covers starting a business and provides up to six-day accommodation after arrival to Georgia.

Since 2003, IOM has implemented a separate EU-funded programme for those who have unlawfully stayed abroad or rejected asylum applicants (SCMI n.d. d). The IOM programme offers consulting, temporary accommodation provision, necessary medication purchase, training and job placement, and assistance in income-generating activities (together with funding) (IOM n.d.; SCMI n.d. d).

There are also other programmes for returnees. Frontex supports EU Member States and Schengen Associated Countries in providing reintegration assistance both during the first days following the arrival in the country of origin (post-arrival assistance), as well as longer-term assistance up to 12 months (post-return assistance). Frontex is not implementing these activities but subcontracting implementing partners (Frontex n.d. a). In the case of Georgia, Frontex works in formal partnership with Caritas International Belgium, which cooperates with Caritas Georgia. The assistance provided by Caritas Georgia within this scheme includes airport pick-up or reception at the place of arrival, temporary accommodation, in-country travel assistance, special assistance for vulnerable people, referral for urgent medical care and cash assistance as post-arrival assistance. Furthermore, post-return assistance is available through business start-up assistance, long-term housing support, social, legal and medical support, job placement, schooling and language training, vocational training, and cash assistance (Frontex n.d. b).

⁵ The programme has annual editions, see e.g. the 2018 edition, see more: (SCMI n.d. e).

There are also programmes developed by countries returning Georgians (sending countries). The returnees can benefit from both the state programme and those implemented by the sending country. For example, the German and French governments developed important programmes. One of the components of the project *Strengthening the Development Potential of the EU Mobility Partnership in Georgia through Targeted Circular Migration and Diaspora Mobilization* (2013-2016) was assistance in the reintegration offered for 40 professionals of the nursing and hospitality sector as well as encouraging 45 Georgians trained in Germany to return home and set up enterprises (SCMI n.d. c). Since 2017, Germany has developed the *Starthilfe* project (implemented by IOM); however, Georgians are eligible only for one-off financial support because reintegration support should be covered within the EU Reintegration Programme (BAMF 2024). There is a special repatriation programme for highly qualified returnees from Germany. Also, the French Office for Immigration and Integration (OFII) supports the programme for Georgian returnees, which aims to assist them in starting businesses. The programme includes social and medical assistance as well as support for professional and economic projects (OFII 2022). Poland has neither introduced any particular reintegration programme nor cooperated with any Polish NGOs on the issue of return and reintegration with the Georgian side.

The statistics on the beneficiaries of all the programmes are as follows. According to the IOM, between 2015 and 2019, there were 4,929 beneficiaries within four programmes: the programme implemented by the IOM (2,607), the Government of Georgia's State Reintegration Programme (987), the project implemented by Caritas (732), and the OFII's reintegration programme (603) (IOM 2021b: 11).

Implementation of the Programmes in Practice

As we were informed within the field study, 'effective implementation of return and readmission policies represents one of the top priorities of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Georgia' (IDI_GE_21). However, as one of our interviewees admitted, 'the State Migrations Reintegration Programme is simply too small. Basically, it has no impact.' (IDI_GE_8-9-10). Another interviewee explained: 'last year, over 900 persons applied for the state reintegration programme, of which only 278 were eligible and provided with support' (IDI_GE_8-9-10). As the study conducted by IOM revealed, the State Programme was used mainly by proactive and independent migrants due to the way of applying for participation (IOM 2021b: 11). Therefore, the programmes developed by various EU Member States seem to fill the gap in the assistance provision of returnees in Georgia. Generally – despite various funding sources – the reintegration support is not offered to all returnees, and the difference between the level of support and services offered to returnees might be confusing.

It is important to remember that externalisation in the case of reintegration of returnees is not limited to the territory of Georgia but also pertains to the pre-departure activities in the EU Member States. As one Georgian NGO worker said, 'the reintegration starts before they [migrants] even are deported. That the first, you know, information about the opportunities in Georgia is given back' (IDI_GE_2-3-4). Thus, the information provision seems to be the crucial factor of reintegration effectiveness.

Strong social links in Georgian society support the effectiveness of the programmes. The employee mentioned above ensured that in the case of accommodation, Georgians can rely on their relatives because, as he said: 'we are believing that if someone find[s] our relatives in the

street, it's our shame' (IDI_GE_11). Other interviewees expressed similar opinions.⁶ Thus, the culture of strong family ties, in particular, is an important element supporting the reintegration of returnees in Georgia, and the reintegration is, to a considerable extent, dependent on social networks. As the recent IOM study revealed, 68% of Georgian returnees from Germany expressed strong community belonging in Georgia (IOM 2024: 48).

The assistance often also encompasses travel arrangements and administrative aid for travel preparations. The businesses set up by returnees are usually small-scale undertakings such as hairdresser salons, washing car services, or tailor workshops (People in Need 2024). There are situations when there is a special need to reintegrate children who spent most (of all) of their life abroad, and they need to 'get private tutoring to enhance their Georgian language skills so that they can join their peers and not the lower grades that correspond to their age because of their language problems' (IDI_GE_8-9-10). Therefore, the programmes developed by the EU Member States also attempt to cover specific needs which are not included in the other programmes.

The NGOs engaged in the reintegration process work closely with beneficiaries to write or correct the business plans. Often, the role of advisors (also known as return/reintegration counsellors) in this process is crucial – one of our interviewees admitted: 'in most cases, we change their business plan with the very close cooperation and negotiation of the beneficiary, because (...) their view about what they can do in Georgia, in Tbilisi, in Kutaisi is much different, different from what they really can do' (IDI_GE_2-3-4). As our interviewees stressed, the organisations implementing the reintegration programmes are also responsible for procuring goods, as the beneficiaries do not receive money for setting up their businesses. Instead, the NGOs purchase necessary items and hand them out to the returnees. The NGO worker quoted above declared: 'We have a very good procurement division that works actively over that because we are eager to find everything with best specifications and lowest prices'. Another person engaged in the preparation of the business plans process said that it 'might spend months working with one beneficiary in terms of making a business plan' because the advisors are 'narrowing down the plan to as tight and suitable for the beneficiary as possible' (IDI_GE_2-3-4). Another person responsible for reintegration programmes listed the most common forms of businesses: 'dairy farms, goat farms, fishery, like land cultivation, like greenhouses, production of dairy products, small production sites, like furniture production or sewing workshops, depending on the experience of a person' (IDI_GE_8-9-10).

The implementing agencies are obliged to monitor the further development of the businesses, which is usually done after one or two years. As our interviewees admitted, the success rate is quite high⁷, and one of our interviewees pointed out that 'there have been some cases [of people] who have been very good and who have expanded their businesses, who have employed some other people' (IDI_GE_8-9-10). However, almost all businesses are rather small and have no employees. The same interviewee summarised the assistance provided within reintegration schemes as crucial for returnees because 'otherwise they would be just returning with their empty hands and then thinking again of going someplace'. However, regarding the monitoring of the businesses of returnees, it is not always possible to reach the beneficiaries. One NGO worker admitted: 'sometimes you're planning your monitoring visit to Kutaisi, for example. They say, are you? [...] Okay, come, I come and they don't answer the phone' (IDI_GE_16-17).

⁶ However, some interviewees pointed out that the pool of accommodation within the state programme is sometimes not sufficient to cover all needs, so the social networks play the crucial role in this case.

⁷ One interviewee estimated it at 85% (IDI_GE_8-9-10).

The funding provided within the partnership with the external actors, the EU included, is crucial for the work done to reintegrate the returnees. Some of our interviewees emphasised the role of external partners and were sceptical about cooperation with the Georgian government. As one of the NGO workers stated: ‘We do not work with the government (...) because [the] government do[es] not really have any kind of programmes to support people who are returning for us to cooperate with them. Okay. Basically, whatever we do about the returnees, about the... this project, what we implement, we work with our partner in [name of the country]. That’s it’ (IDI_GE_2-3-4). Importantly—as our interviewees explained—the money the beneficiaries receive often depends on the country from which they return.

4. Identified Gaps and Shortcomings

According to the opinions of our interviewees, the cooperation between the EU and Georgia on the returns of Georgian citizens will gain importance in the coming years. This will pose a difficulty for the reintegration systems and increase the need to develop the existing programmes or new ones in cooperation with the sending countries or the EU as a whole. Moreover, an NGO worker interviewed by us doubted the successful development of programmes for returnees because – according to this person – ‘the government’s main policy... policies and political like vision about returnees is internal returning and support IDPs, mainly [those] who lost their homes’ (IDI_GE_2-3-4). Therefore, the still unsolved situation of the IDPs (internally displaced persons) from the occupied territories of Abkhazia and South Ossetia can be a burden for the effective development of assistance for returnees from abroad. Our interviewees also doubt the possibility of externalisation in the form of an agreement similar to the UK-Rwanda one (aimed at sending some migrants ordered to leave the UK to Rwanda) or the Italy-Albania one (aimed at keeping the asylum-seekers, who applied for the Italian asylum system, on the territory of Albania). According to the experts we talked to, there is no political discussion about such solutions right now. One of our interviewees ensured that it is ‘unthinkable to create [on Georgian territory] some programme like British people want to do in Rwanda’ (IDI_GE_18-19).

The most significant gaps identified within the study pertain to problems with the effectiveness of the reintegration programs, which make returnees emigrate again to the EU. Also, some structural problems were identified, which could be the factors pushing Georgians to emigrate. One expert involved in the implementation of reintegration policies we interviewed stressed that returnees sometimes do not have trust in the state reintegration programme due to prolonged procedures, and another problem is the short time of the programme (IDI_GE_12). Some interviewees assessed the state integration programme as not satisfying the needs. One public entity representative pointed out that not enough funding was allocated to the reintegration: ‘it [the reintegration programmes] needs to increase their budget because one of the biggest problems is related to the budget’ (GE_14-15). In sum, as one of the international organisations’ representatives told us: ‘Georgians keep on applying for asylum, even though they know that they will not get eligible. But they keep on going there. And the State Migration Reintegration Programme is simply too small. It has no impact.’ (IDI_GE_8-9-10). Based on the research material collected, this migrants’ strategy is difficult to explain. Even the organisations interviewed that draw attention to it do not know what is behind it.

Another problem is the access to information, which makes some returnees unaware of the assistance they can receive. As the official data of Georgian migration institutions show, some

returnees do not know about the reintegration programmes available in Georgia (SCMI 2020). As one of our interviewees claimed, ‘one of the most important component[s] [of the reintegration process] is the information access’ (IDI_GE_8-9-10). A former worker of one international organisation said: ‘using the example of Poland, I can say that Georgian citizens located in Poland, in any voivodeship, do not receive information regarding the possibility of return’ (IDI_GE_25). Some other interviewed experts mentioned misinformation⁸ in Polish detention centres before the departure, which resulted in anger after arrival.

Moreover, those who stayed illegally abroad especially encountered difficulties with reintegration. One of the most problematic issues is the recognition of education certificates and the need for retraining to meet the market demands (SCMI 2020). As one of the public administration employees noted, ‘the professions which Georgian citizens have, it’s not in line with the market demand’ (IDI_GE_11). Unfortunately, the language skills gained during emigration are not always an asset in Georgia because, as one interviewee said, there is no ‘a huge spectrum of international companies’ which can hire people based on a specific foreign language they speak (IDI_GE_13).

Our interviewees also emphasised that in public opinion, returnees may not need much help because they should possess resources achieved during migration: ‘in Georgia, if you stop somebody on the street and ask about migrant, in his or her eyes, [a] migrant is a person with money, with opportunities, and with everything he or she needs’ (IDI_GE_2-3-4). Another interviewee depicted this attitude with the words: ‘When you come back from abroad, everyone thinks of you as rich, no one knows what you earned there, you don’t have anything there, and now you have to help everyone. Well, I think it’s also very burdensome for these people’ (IDI_GE_24). In the opinion of the NGO workers who talked to us, this social attitude towards returnees impacts the psychological state of non-quite-successful returnees and, as a consequence, encourages them to re-emigration. Also, strong pressure on migrants to send as much money home as possible can push them into a precarious position abroad and lead to the need for return.

Another problem is that the national health service does not cover 100% of the costs of medical treatment. According to our interviewees, this can be a push factor for people with serious illnesses if they cannot afford the medical costs. Also, our interviewees noted that it is a problem that some of the business plans are assessed abroad without full knowledge of the market and cultural reality in Georgia.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

Following Russia’s full-scale aggression against Ukraine and the relative ban on the return of Ukrainian citizens to their country of origin from 2022 onwards, it is Georgians who have become one of the dominant groups of foreigners against whom return decisions are issued both in the EU and Poland. Georgia’s cooperation with the EU allows for the smooth implementation of return decisions and the participation of Georgian services (relieving Frontex in this role). Reintegration programmes offered to Georgian citizens on return decisions are not always sufficient to convince Georgian citizens to return. They are also not complete enough, in particular financially, to convince returnees to persist in their resolve to return to their country of origin. It is worth considering extending the reintegration package

⁸ Misinformation about the money available after return is an example. The returnees have not received cash which they were promised and which returnees on the same flight but from other countries were receiving.

and coordinating the amount of support of the various reintegration programmes, which vary widely.

The cooperation established by the EU with Georgia in organising return appears to be working quite well. The involvement of Georgian actors in organising flights and reintegration assistance after return significantly relieves the burden on the EU side (Frontex or individual Member States). However, the question remains whether the ‘pushing’ of the tasks of carrying out air return operations does not entail a reduction in the guarantees to which returned foreigners are entitled. This relates, for example, to issues such as security on board the aircraft and compliance with health protection requirements for persons belonging to vulnerable groups (sick persons, persons with disabilities and pregnant women). Furthermore, whether the Georgian side sufficiently monitors these operations should be considered.

Based on the identified gaps and shortcomings, we recommend what follows. Strengthening access to relevant information prior to departure seems crucial for the effective reintegration process. Information dissemination is essential at all stages of the return process and should be accessible both prior to departure and upon arrival in Georgia, namely in strategic places of first contact like airports, railway stations, and bus stations. Hence, it should be an important part of the cooperation between migration agencies in the EU Member States and in Georgia. We also recommend that, if possible, the training should be accessible before departure so the returnee can find a job immediately after arrival. Furthermore, the results of our study suggest the need to strengthen the role of local NGOs in the implementation of reintegration programmes, which means that as much contextualised knowledge as possible is needed to increase the efficiency of such programmes. This is particularly important in remote mountainous regions of Georgia and those inhabited by ethnic minorities. It would also be beneficial for the effectiveness of reintegration programmes to enhance cooperation between the NGOs supporting migrants in the sending countries and Georgia. Last but not least, we recommend organising information campaigns that can alter the social attitude towards returnees and the requirements that are imposed on them based on the assumption that they are able to support relatives in Georgia instead of requiring support themselves.

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